

**THE ROLE OF SERUM PARAOXONASE IN CONGENITAL
RENO-URINARY ANOMALIES IN CHILDREN**

Rolul paraoxonazei serice în anomaliile congenitale renale-urinare la copii

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Summary. Recently, impressive progress has been made in understanding the etiology and pathophysiological mechanisms involved in renal diseases in pediatric patients. Research shows that current treatment methods can be useful if they are applied to the early stages of the disease and sensitive early biomarkers are identified. In this regard, an important role would be played by the evaluation of serum paraoxonase family proteins at the onset and clinical-evolutionary stages of the pathology. Purpose of the study: Highlighting the pathogenetic role of PON family proteins in the diagnosis, treatment, medical and surgical resolution of children with congenital reno-urinary anomalies (CRUA). Material and methods: The serum level of paraoxonase family proteins (PON) was evaluated in 60 patients aged 0-18 years with CRUA, including 20 – with congenital hydronephrosis (HN), 20 – with vesicoureteral reflux (VUR) and 20 – with megaureterohydronephrosis (MUH). The comparison group (control) consisted of 20 practically healthy children of the same age. The laboratory examination included the evaluation of specially selected serum biomarkers – the level of PON family proteins (PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA). Results: The number of children with ACRU has been shown to increase in recent decades, while the serum level of PON proteins (PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA) has shown a tendency to decrease compared to the control group. Conclusions: The data obtained reveal the informativeness and high value of estimating the serum level of PON family proteins and which can be used as sensitive biomarkers, valuable in assessing the activity of the inflammatory process but also the effectiveness of the applied treatment.

Key words: Congenital reno-urinary anomalies, children, proteins of the paraoxonase family.

Introduction

There has been a significant increase in interest in the study of human paraoxonase (PON) – a family of proteins encoded by genes that include paraoxonase 1, 2 and 3 (PON1, PON2 and PON3). Paraoxonase 1 is known for its ability to hydrolyze a wide range of substrates, including organophosphorus compounds, toxic nerve gases and aromatic carboxylic acid esters. Several recent studies have highlighted the involvement of PON1 in modulating the ability of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) to protect against the atherogenesis process and its clinical manifestations. PON1 possesses antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities, being involved in the regulation of the antiatherogenic activity of HDL, i.e. in the regulation of the reverse cholesterol transport process. Although epidemiological studies have shown that there is an inverse relationship between HDL levels and cardiovascular risk, several studies have emphasized the importance of HDL functionality in protecting against cardiovascular diseases (CVD). Given that PON1 is involved in several atheroprotective functions of HDL, elucidation of the mechanisms by which PON1 modulates HDL functionality, as well as identification of interventions that stimulate PON1 activity and/or increase plasma concentrations of this protein are of great practical interest¹.

Material and methods. The serum level of paraoxonase 1 family proteins (PON1) was assessed in 60 patients aged 0-18 years with congenital reno-urinary anomalies (CRUA), including 20 – with congenital hydronephrosis (HN), 20 – with vesicoureteral reflux (VUR) and 20 – with megaureterohydronephrosis (MUH). The comparison group consisted of 20 practically healthy children of the same age (control). The paraclinical examination included the assessment of specially selected serum biomarkers – the level of PON1 proteins (PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA).

¹ Samouilidou, E.C.; Liaouri, A.; Kostopoulos, V.; Nikas, D.; Grapsa, E. The importance of paraoxonase 1 activity in chronic kidney disease, in: *Renal Failure*, 2024, vol. 46, nr. 2. DOI: 10.1080/0886022X.2024.2376930.

Results. The level of PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA indices in malformations and renal diseases in children is presented in table 1 and fig. 1 and 2, from which we deduce the decrease of PON phenylacetate values in all research groups. Regarding PON pNitroFA, the results obtained reveal a more relevant inhibitory effect on this index in children with RVU and MUH (table 1, fig. 1 and 2).

Table 1. Changes in PON protein levels (PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA) in children with malformations and renal diseases

Research groups	PON phenylacetate, $\mu\text{M}/\text{min}/\text{L}$	PON (pNitroPhA), $\mu\text{M}/\text{min}/\text{L}$
Control (7.00; 10.40)	8.98 \pm 2,30; 8.41; IQR 3.40 (3.53; 4.36)	3.97; IQR 0.84 4.12 \pm 0.95;
HN i/o	8,32 \pm 3.16; 7,35; IQR 3.65 (6.31; 9.95); $p_1=0.779$	3.12 \pm 0.82; 2.78; IQR 1.19 (1.93; 4.94); $p_1=0.003$
HN p/o	8.51 \pm 1.72; 8,03; IQR 3.09 (7.17;10.26); $p_1=0.966$; $p_2=0.856$	3.25 \pm 0.56; 3.29; IQR 1.13 (2.14; 3.98); $p_1=0.001$; $p_2=0.000$
RVU i/o	8.02 \pm 1.53; 8.33; IQR 1.84 (7.50; 9.74); $p_1=0.51$	3.32 \pm 0.51; 3.30; IQR 0.83 (2.89;3.72); $p_1=0.001$
RVU p/o	7.75 \pm 1.58; 7.53; IQR 2.47 (7.30; 9.74); $p_1=0.102$; $p_2=0.080$	2.96 \pm 0.69*; 2.85; IQR 1.17 (2.28; 3.38); $p_1=0.000$; $p_2=0.040$
MUH i/o	7.32 \pm 1.60; 7.70; IQR 2.46 (6.16; 8.62); $p_1=0.031$	2.76 \pm 0.44**; 2.80; IQR 0.63 (2.41; 3.02); $p_1=0,000$
MUH p/o	7.72 \pm 2.61; 7.56; IQR 5.27 (5,34; 10,62); $p_1=0.433$; $p_2=0.48$	3.02 \pm 0.88*; 2.96; IQR 1.45 (2.18; 3.63); $p_1=0.000$; $p_2=0.455$

Legend: HN, hydronephrosis; RVU, reflux vesicoureteral; MUH, megaureterohydronephrosis; i/o, intraoperative; p/o, postoperative; **PON phenylacetate**, phenylacetate paraoxonase/arylesterase activity; **PON (pNitroPhA)**, phenylacetate paraoxonase/arylesterase activity; Statistical significance, p_1 -compared to control; p_2 – compared to i/o group

Fig. 1. Activity of PON phenylacetate (phenylacetate paraoxonase/arylesterase activity) in blood serum in children with malformations and renal diseases depending on the form of the disease (%).

Fig. 2. PON p-Nitrophenyl acetate activity (phenylacetate paraoxonase/aryles-terase activity) in blood serum in children with malformations and renal diseases depending on the form of the disease (%).

Discussion. Paraoxonase 1 (PON1) is an important antioxidant enzyme associated with high-density lipoproteins (HDL), being involved in the pathogenesis of many diseases, including chronic kidney disease (CKD). The decrease in serum PON1 activity observed in CKD patients is linked to an increased vulnerability to atherosclerosis. Of note is the association of PON1 activity with oxidative stress, the impact of genetic polymorphism on disease development, the effect of drugs and nutritional status. In addition, there is strong evidence supporting the involvement of reduced PON1 activity in the incidence of cardiovascular disease in CKD patients. PON1 is a valuable biomarker for assessing antioxidant status with a prognostic benefit on clinical outcomes in different stages of CKD². In order to clarify the involvement of the PON protein family, especially PON phenylacetate and PON pNitroFA in modulating the ability of HDL to protect against the atherogenesis process, we have performed for the first time a study of the changes in the level of these indices in children with malformations and reno-urinary diseases. The data obtained reveal a decrease in PON-1 activity in these patients.

PON1 is a calcium-dependent aryldialkyl phosphatase and a component of HDL, associated with apolipoprotein Ai (apo A-i) and apolipoprotein J (apo-J), also known as clusterin (CLU), a multifunctional glycoprotein that plays a crucial role in various biological processes³, being synthesized predominantly in the liver, then secreted into the circulation and delivered to target tissues by binding to HDL⁴.

² Roller, V.; Ciuntu, A.; Țarcă, E.; et al. Prenatal Diagnosis of Reno-Urinary Malformations in a Tertiary Center of Republic of Moldavia, in: *Diagnostics*, 2024, vol. 14, nr. 19, art. 2243. DOI: 10.3390/diagnostics14192243.

³ Mackness, M.; Mackness, B. Human paraoxonase-1 (PON1): gene structure and expression, promiscuous activities and multiple physiological roles, in: *Gene*, 2015, vol. 567, nr. 1, pp. 12–21; James, R.; Deakin, S. The importance of high-density lipoproteins for paraoxonase-1 secretion, stability, and activity, in: *Free Radic Biol Med*, 2004, vol. 37, nr. 12, pp. 1986–1994; Kelso, G.; Stuart, W.; Richter, R.; et al. Apolipoprotein J is associated with paraoxonase in human plasma, in: *Biochemistry*, 1994, vol. 33, nr. 3, pp. 832–839.

⁴ Précourt, L.P.; Amre, D.; Denis, A.M.; et al. The three-gene paraoxonase family: physiologic roles, actions and regulation, in: *Atherosclerosis*, 2011, vol. 214, nr. 1, pp. 20–36.

The CLU protein is widely distributed in the body, including peripheral organs, brain and fluids such as plasma, urine, cerebrospinal fluid, seminal fluid and tears. The functions of CLU in peripheral tissues have been well studied and include the clearance of misfolded proteins, lipid transport, inhibition of the complement system, and regulation of oxidative stress and cell death⁵.

PON1 can hydrolyze a wide variety of substrates, thus having multiple important physiological activities and functions:

i) PON1 can hydrolyze organophosphorus compounds such as paraoxon (paraoxonase activity), which explains its ability to hydrolyze organophosphorus insecticides,

ii) PON1 can hydrolyze aromatic carboxylic acid esters such as phenyl acetate (arylesterase activity),

iii) PON1 is involved in the metabolism of homocysteine (Hcy) – a non-proteinogenic AA formed upon demethylation of methionine, and hyperhomocysteinemia is responsible for a range of toxic effects such as neurotoxicity, homocysteinylated proteins which is detrimental to their structure and function. The links between PON1 and Hcy with pathological conditions such as atherosclerosis, coronary heart disease, stroke, diabetes mellitus, renal failure and Alzheimer's disease are described in a number of studies, including recent ones⁶.

iv) On the other hand, PON1 hydrolyzes phospholipid hydroperoxides, contributing largely to the detoxification of oxidative stress mediators and explaining the antioxidant and anti-inflammatory potential of the enzyme^{3,4}. Most often in renal diseases, paraoxonase and arylesterase activities are evaluated⁷. PON1 is located in the proximal renal tubules, which are particularly susceptible to the toxic effects of endotoxins, xenobiotics, which are filtered by the glomeruli and reabsorbed in the renal tubules into the extracellular fluid, from where they then enter the blood serum again⁸. PON1 plays a cardinal role in the regulation of renal inflammation and fibrosis⁹.

v) Atherosclerosis – the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in the world, is a chronic multifactorial inflammatory disease that involves a complex interaction of circulating cells and blood factors with blood vessels. The disease begins with endothelial dysfunction, which leads to the accumulation of oxidized lipids in the arterial wall, and oxidized lipids in turn play a central role in atherogenesis by inducing a proinflammatory phenotype in the arterial wall and which underlies the development and progression of atherosclerosis¹⁰.

vi) There are a number of factors that oppose the development of atherogenesis. One of these antiatherogenic protective factors is high-density lipoprotein (HDL) due to its ability

⁵ Khalil, A.; Fulop, T.; Berrougui, H. Role of Paraoxonase 1 in the Regulation of High-Density Lipoprotein Functionality and in Cardiovascular Protection, in: *Antioxid Redox Signal*, 2021, vol. 34, nr. 3, pp. 191–200.

⁶ Humphreys, D. T.; Carver, J. A.; et al. Clusterin Has Chaperone-like Activity Similar to That of Small Heat Shock Proteins, in: *J Biol Chem*, 1999, vol. 274, nr. 11, pp. 6875–6881.

⁷ Perla-Kaján, J.; Jakubowski, H. Paraoxonase 1 and homocysteine metabolism, in: *Amino Acids*, 2012, vol. 43, nr. 4, p. 1405–1417; Durrington, P. N.; Bashir, B.; Soran, H. Paraoxonase 1 and atherosclerosis, in: *Front Cardiovasc Med*, 2023, vol. 10, art. 1065967. DOI: 10.3389/fcvm.2023.1065967.

⁸ Khersonsky, O.; Tawfik, D. S. Structure-reactivity studies of serum paraoxonase PON1 suggest that its native activity is lactonase, in: *Biochemistry*, 2005, vol. 44, nr. 16, pp. 6371–6382.

⁹ Yilmaz, N. Relationship between paraoxonase and homocysteine: crossroads of oxidative diseases, in: *Arch Med Sci*, 2012, vol. 8, nr. 1, pp. 138–153.

¹⁰ Rodrigo, I.; Hernández, A.; López-Caballero, J.; et al. Immunohistochemical evidence for the expression and induction of paraoxonase in rat liver, kidney and brain tissue. Implications for its physiological role, in: *Chem Biol Interact*, 2001, vol. 137, nr. 2, pp. 123–137.

to mediate reverse cholesterol transport, as well as its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and endothelial protective functions¹¹.

vii) HDL can inhibit endothelial cell adhesion molecules, such as vascular cell adhesion molecule 1 (VCAM-1), intercellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), and E-selectin, which allow monocytes to adhere to sites of atherosclerosis⁷.

viii) HDL can remove peroxidized lipids from low-density lipoproteins (LDL) and subsequently reduce them by a reaction with the methionine residues of apolipoprotein A1.

ix) A number of HDL-associated enzymes, including paraoxonase 1 (PON1), are also involved in the anti-oxidative, anti-inflammatory and endothelial protective functions of HDL.

The anti-inflammatory activity of PON1 is determined by: a) attenuation of endothelial secretion of chemoattractant protein-1 (MCP-1), responsible for the recruitment of monocytes into the subendothelial space and migration to the site of inflammation where they transform into macrophages and, subsequently, foam cells; b) inhibition of intracellular adhesion molecule-1 (ICAM-1), an inflammatory factor, which determines the oxidation of LDL; c) hydrolysis of platelet-activating factor (PAF), a proinflammatory mediator, which stimulates monocyte migration and their transformation into macrophages; d) inhibition of the secretion of proinflammatory cytokines (TNF-alpha, IL-1; IL-6) by macrophages. It has been shown that PON1 could have beneficial effects on numerous multifactorial diseases, such as atherosclerosis, CVD, diabetes mellitus and neurodegenerative diseases by modulating relevant signaling pathways involved in inflammation and oxidative stress (OS). These pathways include the peroxisome proliferator-activated receptor gamma (PPAR- γ) and the protein kinase B/nuclear factor kappa-enhancer of activated B cells light chains (AKT/NF-kB)-dependent signaling pathways.

In the pathogenesis and progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD), a decisive role is played by the exacerbation of OS, caused by elevated plasma homocysteine (Hcy) levels and low antioxidant levels. Folic acid treatment significantly improves the estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) and these effects are mediated by increased PON1 activity.

PON1, a calcium-dependent hydrolytic enzyme, is expressed in the liver, kidney, colon and brain¹² and then enters the bloodstream attached to HDL. Transcriptomic and proteomic analyses have provided new insights into PON1 function by identifying proteins and molecular pathways affected by PON1 depletion or PON1 overexpression. Accumulating evidence shows that changes in PON1 expression/activity influence both extracellular and cellular proteostasis (proteostasis is the process of maintaining the conformational and functional integrity of the proteome) by affecting epigenetic regulation, upregulation of target of rapamycin (mTOR) signaling, and inhibition of autophagy. Changes in gene expression caused by low levels of PON1 expression/activity are exacerbated by the metabolic stress of hyperlipidemia or hyperhomocysteinemia. Although these changes are linked to CVD, Alzheimer's disease, and cancer, the molecular mechanisms by which PON1 affects gene expression remain to be elucidated in future studies¹³.

¹¹ Khalaf, F. K.; Mohammed, C. J.; Dube, P.; et al. Paraoxonase-1 Regulation of Renal Inflammation and Fibrosis in Chronic Kidney Disease, in: *Antioxidants*, 2022, vol. 11, art. 900. DOI: 10.3390/antiox11050900.

¹² Jebari-Benslaiman, S.; Galicia-García, U.; Larrea-Sebal, A.; et al. Pathophysiology of Atherosclerosis, in: *Int J Mol Sci*, 2022, vol. 23, nr. 6, art. 3346. DOI: 10.3390/ijms23063346.

¹³ Jakubowski, H. The Molecular Bases of Anti-Oxidative and Anti-Inflammatory Properties of Paraoxonase 1, in: *Antioxidants*, 2024, vol. 13, nr. 11, art. 1292. DOI: 10.3390/antiox13111292;

Conclusions

The data obtained reveal the informativeness and high value of estimating the serum level of PON family proteins and which can be used as sensitive biomarkers, valuable in assessing the activity of the inflammatory process but also the effectiveness of the applied treatment.

Matsumoto, A.; Maes, M.; Michelin, A. P.; et al. Treatment With Folic Acid Increases Paraoxonase 1 Activity Thereby Improving Chronic Kidney Disease, in: *Preprints*, 2020. DOI: 10.20944/preprints202003.0472.v1